

Adaptive Phototaxis in Response to Experience – Learning by Association in the Slime Mold *Physarum polycephalum*

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Abstract: Cognitive processes such as learning by association are traditionally considered exclusive to organisms with nervous systems. However, increasing evidence suggests that some aneural organisms, such as the slime mold *Physarum polycephalum*, exhibit behaviors indicative of basal cognition. In this study, we investigated whether *P. polycephalum* is capable of associative learning by combining light stimuli with food rewards. Using a controlled light gradient environment, we conducted three experiments: training plasmodia to move toward an aversive blue light, toward a neutral red light, and away from neutral red light. Following initial baseline tests, plasmodia underwent four training sessions with food cues, after which their phototactic behavior was reassessed without food. Results show that plasmodia significantly altered their behavior when trained toward both aversive and neutral stimuli, with the strongest effect observed in the aversive (blue light) condition. While these behavioral shifts suggest associative learning, the potential role of habituation could not be fully excluded. Our findings contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting cognitive-like capacities in aneural organisms and highlight the need for further investigation into the mechanisms underlying memory and learning in *Physarum*.

Keywords: aneural cognition, basal organisms, habituation, learning by association.

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Introduction

Cognition and learning have long been thought of as properties unique to animals with nervous systems. In the last 30 years, however, increased research has been conducted on adaptive behavior in organisms without nervous systems. Aneural cognition – sometimes called minimal or basal cognition (Lyon 2020) – is still viewed as controversial among the cognitive sciences (Lyon et al. 2021). Nonetheless, a growing body of evidence shows reactions in aneural organisms that would be deemed cognition in organisms with brains. Therefore, new frameworks have been developed to categorize the behavior of aneural organisms to keep them comparable to what is traditionally thought of as cognition

(Lyon et al. 2021; Manicka and Levin 2019). These frameworks allow for a more structured evaluation of cognitive capabilities in asexual organisms, such as unicellular amoebae.

The acellular slime mold *Physarum polycephalum* is a compelling model organism for the study of adaptive behavior in a unicellular organism. During its vegetative state, *Physarum* forms a multinucleated syncytium called plasmodium. Plasmodia resemble macroscopic amoeboid cells and can easily grow up to a few centimeters in diameter, moving by extending filament-like pseudopodia (Rojas and Stephenson 2021). *Physarum* is capable of sensing its environment in various ways. It is capable of processing chemical stimuli (Carlile 1970; McClory and Cooté 1985), can distinguish between various wavelengths of light (Adamatzky 2013), seek out optimal temperatures (Wolf et al. 1997), as well as react to gravity (Block et al. 1992; Wolke et al. 1987), magnetic fields (Shirakawa et al. 2012) and vibration (Gehrke and Freiberg 2025).

These features are prerequisites for learning: *Physarum* actively forages in its environment, interacting with and reacting to the above-mentioned stimuli. Furthermore, it is capable of modifying its responses to stimuli. *Physarum* has been shown to habituate to aversive stimuli, learning to ignore them over time (Boisseau et al. 2016) and even sharing the learned behavior with previously naïve plasmodia (Vogel and Dussutour 2016). Further complex information processing includes complex decision making (Dussutour et al. 2010) and anticipation of rhythmic events (Saigusa et al. 2008).

Overall, *Physarum* shows a degree of environmental awareness, behavioral flexibility and complexity often associated with nervous systems. According to the framework given by Lyon et al. (2021), it shows many capacities listed in the proposed toolkit of basal cognitive abilities. Therefore, it is of particular interest to explore the limits of *Physarum* cognition. An especially difficult task is learning by association, as it does not only involve adaptive behavior but also the integration of multiple sensory inputs into new meaningful environmental interactions (Loy et al. 2021).

The first and only experiment concerning learning by association in *Physarum polycephalum* has been conducted by Shirakawa et al. (2011). The authors aimed to change the plasmodium's natural thermotaxis response using food as an additional stimulus. This was done by placing a plasmodium in the center of a chamber with a controlled temperature gradient to provide a colder (aversive) and warmer (attractive) side. Food was placed on the colder side, and the plasmodium was observed for seven days. For the first three days, the plasmodium showed the normal thermotactic behavior of moving toward the warmer side. Subsequently, the plasmodium started moving toward the colder side, apparently reversing its thermotaxis due to associating cold with nutrition. The authors themselves, however, conclude that this experiment does not prove learning by association, but may instead be explained by habituation to the cold (Shirakawa et al. 2011).

Inspired by that experiment, we developed a similar approach using gradients of light to test *Physarum* learning. Light was used instead of temperature since light can be, depending on its wavelength and intensity, both an aversive and a positive stimulus (Adamatzky 2013), possibly even a neutral stimulus. Therefore, we tried to train *Physarum* to move toward an aversive stimulus, toward a neutral stimulus and away from that neutral stimulus. The aim of this study is to further explore possible associative learning with both neutral and aversive stimuli to distinguish association from habituation.

Materials and methods

The plasmodia used in all experiments were grown from a single sclerotium of unknown age that was purchased online from a commercial provider. According to the provider, the original plasmodium was collected in a forest in Germany. After resuscitation in our lab (Fig. 1), the plasmodium was maintained and regularly divided to form a clonal line. In one clone, sporulation was induced to morphologically confirm the species, because that is only possible by examination of the spores (Nannenga-Bremekamp 2022). Except during the experiments, the plasmodia of this clone line were kept at 20°C in total darkness on 12x12cm Petri-dishes filled with nutrition-free 2%-water agar (20g Agar Agar (CarlRoth GmbH) per 1000ml tap water).

Each plasmodium was maintained every two days by resettling to a fresh Petri-dish, provided with fresh food in the form of rolled oat flakes (Koelln-Flocken, Peter Kölln GmbH & Co. KGaA) and sprayed with demineralized water to raise humidity. During this procedure, each plasmodium was exposed to light for up to 30 minutes. During growth the plasmodia were regularly divided onto multiple Petri-dishes thus growing the clonal line to supply material for the experiments.

Figure 1. Photograph of the fruiting bodies of the used *Physarum*-culture. A voucher-specimen will be placed at the collection of the Senckenberg-Museum in Görlitz (Germany).

Experiments

All experiments were conducted in a custom-made wooden box designed to minimize outside influences. The design of the box is shown in Fig. 2. The box was divided into two parts: one half was equipped with an LED light strip for illumination, while the other was kept dark. A black divider was hung in the middle of the box, dividing both halves and blocking part of the light from entering the darker side, forming a pronounced light gradient. The temperature of the room was kept at 20°C during the experiments. The temperature inside the box was stable at 20°C on both sides of the box.

Figure 2. Visualization of the experimental setup. A. Side-view of the experimental box in which the slime molds were tested and trained. B. Top view of the Petri-dish prepared for the experiment. C. Photograph of a Petri-dish after the experiment. The letter D indicates the dark side, showing that *Physarum* has fully moved away from the light after being placed in the middle of the dish.

For stimulation, an LED light-strip containing multiple LEDs (SimpLED RGB Komplettsset 1.5m, 8W, Paulmann Licht GmbH, Springe-Völksen, Germany) was used, as it was both capable of dimming to regulate the light intensity and of emitting multiple wavelengths. For the experiments, blue light and red light were used since these are relevant for *Physarum* phototaxis (Adamatzky 2013). Spectral analysis of the chosen stimuli revealed narrow wavelength distributions with peaks around 630nm for the red light, and 465nm for the blue light.

For each trial, 2% water agar Petri-dishes similar to those used to cultivate the plasmodia were divided by cutting out a channel of approximately 1cm diameter through the middle. Since *Physarum* prefers to stay on the agar, it was forced to make a decision toward or away from the stimulus, simplifying the analysis by dividing the Petri-dish into two halves. During the experiments, each plasmodium was placed in the middle of the channel on an agar square of approximately 15x15mm. The plasmodia were always scraped onto the agar in order to destroy any pre-existing structures and movement directions. To ease the stress of reorganization, a single oat flake was additionally placed on the plasmodium in the middle of the square.

Each plasmodium underwent an initial testing session, then four consecutive training sessions, and then a final testing session. A visualization of the procedure can be found in Fig. 3. For the testing sessions, no other food was added. During the training sessions, however, a trace of four oat flakes was added to lead the plasmodium into the desired direction. The aim of providing a trace of food was to attract the plasmodia into the intended direction, because it has been shown that *Physarum* is capable of following traces of food (Reid et al. 2016). It is, however, unclear whether they are capable of sensing unscented oat

flakes over distances, therefore the first flake of the food trace was always placed to touch the plasmodium and thus promote movement into that direction. Following a 48 hour exploration period, the spatial distribution of the plasmodium was documented using a high-definition document camera (Optoma DC455, Optoma Europe Ltd., London).

For the main experiments, each test spanned 12 days, during which images were captured and the plasmodium was transferred to a fresh Petri-dish every 2 days. A total of three distinct experiments were conducted. In Experiment 1, aversive blue light was used, and the plasmodia were guided toward the blue light during the training sessions. In Experiment 2, neutral red light was used, and the plasmodia were guided toward the red light during training. In Experiment 3, the setup was similar to Experiment 2, but the plasmodia were trained away from the red light to move into darkness instead. For each of the 3 experiments, a total of 16 plasmodia was used. Before the main experiments, pretests were conducted to find the ideal light intensities for the main experiments. *Physarum* reacts differently to different intensities of light, therefore for the blue light the aim was to find an intensity that was aversive for *Physarum*. In the case of the red light, the aim was to find an intensity that would elicit neither positive nor negative phototaxis to provide a truly neutral stimulus. For the pretests, various light intensities were tested on four plasmodia each, using the setup described for testing without traces of oat flakes. The intensities are given in percentages as fractions of the possible output (152lm) of the LEDs.

Figure 3. Visualization of the experimental procedure. A. Schematic representation of the experimental process inside the box, with manual maintenance and imaging every 48 hours, for a total of 12 days. P denotes the initial position of the *Physarum*, D denotes the dark side, and L denotes the illuminated side of the dish. B. Schematic representation of the three experiments: Experiment 1 - training toward blue light; Experiment 2 - training toward red light; Experiment 3 training to avoid red light.

Data analysis

The images obtained during the initial and final testing sessions were analyzed using the open source platform FIJI (Schindelin et al. 2012), determining the surface area of the plasmodia separately for both field halves, measured in pixels. From these pixels, individual percentages of *Physarum* detected for each image were calculated and statistical analysis was performed using paired t-Tests. All datasets contained multiple instances of extreme values of either 0% or 100%. Due to the particular distribution of the data that prohibited the use of the Wilcoxon-Tests because of the high number of ties, additionally non-parametric Sign-Tests were performed as well to account for the possible unreliability of the t-tests due to violation of requirements. Moreover, the images obtained after the training sessions were evaluated manually to determine the number of oat flakes reached during each session to quantify the plasmodial progress during learning.

Results

To determine the light intensity of the LED-strip in the main experiments, pretests were conducted, using percentages of the maximum light intensity the LEDs could produce to gauge the reaction of the plasmodia. The results of the pretests are shown in Table 1. Due to the aversive reaction observed at higher light intensities, 10% of the maximum blue light intensity was deemed an ideal light strength for Experiment 1. Due to the success at the shown intensities, no higher intensities were tested for the blue light. For the red light, the goal was to find an intensity that would elicit a neutral response. In the intensities from 100% to 50%, an aversive reaction could be observed. At 25% light intensity, *Physarum* showed movement toward the light. 10% light intensity was chosen for the second and third experiments because it led to an even spread of *Physarum* in both directions and was therefore deemed neutral.

Table 1. Results of the pretests, showing the mean percentage of surface area spread of *Physarum* toward the light and the dark side under various light intensities. SEM= standard error of the mean.

Color	Light intensity	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i> % light	<i>M</i> % dark	SEM% light
Red	100%	4	0.147	0.853	0.147
Red	75%	4	0.246	0.754	0.226
Red	50%	4	0.256	0.744	0.248
Red	25%	4	0.750	0.250	0.250
Red	10%	4	0.444	0.556	0.163
Blue	25%	4	0.282	0.718	0.241
Blue	10%	4	0.153	0.847	0.120

Due to the stressful procedure of scraping, not all plasmodia survived the testing periods. For all analyses, only data from surviving plasmodia were used. The number of plasmodia, results of the statistical tests and the mean percentages of plasmodium spread both into the light and dark half of the Petri-dish are listed in Table 2.

To test if *Physarum* would choose to move toward aversive blue light after training more than during the initial testing, a one-tailed paired t-test and a one-tailed paired sign-test were conducted. Both showed a significant increase in surface area after training (p t-test = .015, p sign-test = .011). The same tests were applied to the next paradigm to test if *Physarum* would spread more toward red light after

training. However, despite a tendency of increase visible in the mean percentage, both tests showed no significant increase in surface area (p t-test = .305, p sign-test = .055). Finally, to test if the surface area spread toward light would decrease after training toward darkness, the aforementioned tests were calculated showing a significant change (p t-test = .029, p sign-test = .028). The different mean percentages are depicted in Fig. 3.

Table 2. Results of the main experiments including mean percentage of surface spread toward the light, SEM and the results of the paired t-tests and nonparametric paired sign-tests. SEM = standard error of mean.

Experiment	Stimulus	Goal	n	Before training		After training		$p_{t\text{-Test}}$	$p_{\text{Sign-Test}}$
				$M\%$ light	SEM	$M\%$ light	SEM		
1	Blue	Light	13	.10	.088	.60	.143	.015 *	.011 *
2	Red	Light	13	.45	.145	.75	.128	.305	.055
3	Red	Dark	15	.70	.125	.25	.120	.029 *	.028 *

Note. The results are ordered by which color of light was used (Blue in Experiment 1, Red in Experiment 2 and 3) and the direction toward which the plasmodia were trained (toward light in Experiment 1 and 2, away from the light in Experiment 3). Significant p -values are denoted with an asterisk.

Figure 3. Changes in phototactic behavior before and after training. Mean proportion of *Physarum polycephalum* surface area located on the illuminated side of the Petri dish during the initial (pre-training) and final (post-training) test sessions. Experiment 1 used aversive blue light and trained plasmodia toward the illuminated side. Experiment 2 used neutral red light and trained plasmodia toward the illuminated side. Experiment 3 used neutral red light and trained plasmodia toward the dark side. Higher values indicate a greater proportion of plasmodial movement toward the illuminated side. Error bars represent \pm SEM.

Discussion

Associative learning as a sign of complex information processing is an evolutionary milestone that has only been rarely shown in asexual organisms. The only study addressing learning by association in the slime mold *Physarum polycephalum* by Shirakawa et al. (2011) showed a movement towards an aversive temperature stimulus after training with food as reward. Although the results pointed toward a change in thermotactic behavior, it was not possible to differentiate between true associative learning and simpler habituation. The aim of this study was to expand the behavioral analysis using various light stimuli instead of temperature, and using not only aversive, but also neutral stimuli. This was done to differentiate between habituation and learning by association, since while a change in response to an aversive stimulus might be caused by habituation, a systematic change in response to a neutral stimulus cannot. Altogether, three experiments were conducted: training toward an aversive stimulus, training toward a neutral stimulus and training away from a neutral stimulus.

Experiment 1: Training toward an aversive stimulus

The results of Experiment 1 seem to be in line with the findings of Shirakawa et al. (2011), as an initial aversion to the aversive stimulus was observed that is significantly decreased after four consecutive training sessions. Despite our use of a different aversive stimulus, this result shows that a change in behavior is possible in *Physarum* (in this case phototaxis) after a period of training, and that *Physarum* performs the new behavior even after training in the absence of the nutrition used as incentive. This is only possible through the formation of memory. Nevertheless this result alone does not allow to infer learning by association. It is already known that *Physarum* is capable of ignoring aversive light in the acquisition of nutrients (Latty and Beekman 2010), and that it is capable of habituating to aversive stimuli through consecutive exposure (Boisseau et al. 2016). It is therefore likely that the food trails leading towards the blue light in our study have led to a high exposure to the aversive stimulus as the plasmodia were incentivized to move towards it instead of away, thereby facilitating the process of habituation. Even so, the result shows that habituation is not only possible to cold (Shirakawa et al. 2011) or chemical stimuli such as quinine (Boisseau et al. 2016), but also to light.

Experiment 2: Training toward a neutral stimulus

The second experiment was conducted to test if *Physarum* is able to associate a neutral stimulus with food as positive stimulus to alter the phototactic response. During the initial testing, the plasmodia preferred neither darkness nor red light, and after the training phase no statistically significant change occurred despite an increase of spread toward the red light. While the tendency is in line with the hypothesis that learning by association would lead to a preference for red light, the non-significant effect might either be a product of chance or due to a too small sample size and can therefore not be seen as proof of associative learning.

Experiment 3: Training away from a neutral stimulus

The results of this experiment show a significant decrease of spread toward the red light between the initial and the final training session. This can be interpreted as a sign of associative learning, as it shows that a significant change in behavior towards a neutral stimulus occurred over the course of the consecutive training sessions. It must be mentioned, however, that the movement towards the red light was unusually high during initial testing despite no change in the experimental setup, indicating a high variation in response toward red light. In spite of this observation, the significant systematic change in phototactic response implies a process of learning that, unlike the results of Experiment 1, cannot be explained by habituation. Both the literature (Adamatzky 2013; Hato et al. 1976) and the results of this study show that red light in the used intensity is not an aversive stimulus, and that it may even function as an attractant. Therefore, the observed behavior may be interpreted as learning by association.

General Discussion

Our results show that systematic behavioral change, or learning, can occur in *Physarum* due to the combination of aversive or neutral stimuli with sources of nutrition. While the results are not completely conclusive, in two of the experiments significant changes in phototactic behavior were observed. Habituation alone does not explain the result of Experiment 3 and the tendency observed in Experiment 2; therefore, it is not possible to rule out learning by association.

The mechanism behind the behavioral change is unclear, but it is possible to propose explanations from what is already known in literature. As *Physarum* does not produce electrical action potentials, information processing and learning occur differently from neural systems. Instead, it has been proposed that *Physarum* uses its structure to store information (Cheng 2022), and the interplay of the oscillations in these structures for information processing (Boussard et al. 2021). In the present work, these two elements cannot be the only factor influencing plasmodial behavior, since between each session, the macrostructure of the plasmodia was destroyed by scraping the plasmodia onto new Petri-dishes.

Baluška and Levin (2016) suggest that the cytoskeleton, DNA-methylation and bioelectricity are possible mechanisms for information retention in unicellular organisms. In this case, bioelectricity does not refer to action-potentials but instead the shifting concentration of ions along the cell membranes that can be interpreted as signaling cues among the cells (Zhang and Levin 2025). None of these can be ruled out, even though the cytoskeleton of Amoebozoa such as *Physarum* is very different from other eukaryotes, allowing for the slime mold's constant change of shape (Tekle and Williams 2016). It is also possible that memory in *Physarum* is formed by an interplay of macrostructure, oscillation and cell physiology: While the macrostructure of the tubuli is spontaneously formed during plasmodial movement as a reaction to stimuli, which in turn is mediated by oscillations, it can be thought of as a "short-term memory" in the slime mold. As our results show, this memory can then be transferred into a form of "long-term memory" possibly based on epigenetics and/or bioelectricity. This might lead to the reconstruction of previously successful behavioral patterns such as a particular expansion toward a light gradient that previously led to successful foraging, even after destruction of the plasmodium's physical structures, possibly explaining the behaviors observed in our study.

One challenge in testing association with a neutral stimulus is finding a stimulus that does not elicit a specific response by itself but can still be perceived by the organism. In *Physarum*, perception of a stimulus is mainly assessed by testing if it shows either a positive or a negative response, i.e. moving toward or away from the stimulus. Therefore, proof of stimulus detection in *Physarum* is always associated with assigning valence to the stimulus. Red light was chosen here, because *Physarum* has an ambivalent response to it- while higher intensities are proven to be aversive, lower intensities seem to elicit positive phototaxis (Hato et al. 1976). This effect could be replicated in this study, as seen in Table 1. Therefore, we strived to find an intensity of light that would elicit no phototaxis, hoping that it was still perceptible to the plasmodia but having no positive or aversive effect. The observed change in behavior in Experiment 2 and 3 might serve as an indicator for red light perception in the plasmodia, as the light gradient was the only marker of direction the plasmodia could have used.

Building on these results, more work is needed to further explore the observed behavioral change in *Physarum*. Repeating the experiments with higher numbers of plasmodia can help clarify whether the result observed in Experiment 2 was a product of chance or of learning, while observing oscillations and bioelectricity in the plasmodia during the experiments might help unravel the mechanisms involved in the behavioral changes. Further controls could be realized by either keeping *Physarum* in the setup without food trails or with randomized food trails to assess if changes in behavior still occur, such as habituation. At the same time, replicating and expanding the experimental setup opens the possibility of new cognitive tasks such as reverse-learning, and possibly the identification of other neutral stimuli. Since it has been shown that *Physarum* is capable of sharing learned behavior through exchange of cytoplasm (Vogel and Dussutour 2016), it would be also be of great interest to investigate if the change in phototaxis can be transmitted as well.

Overall, this study demonstrates that *Physarum* is capable of learning by association, leading to a further establishment of cognition in an aneural organism.

Open Practices Statement

The original data presented in this study are openly available in OSF at <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/PVNJK> (accessed on 13 May 2025). The experiments were not preregistered.

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